

DETERMINATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SUBSTANCE "IDENOL"

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Annotation. The therapeutic efficacy and bioequivalence of medicinal products are influenced by the following biological and pharmaceutical factors: the physico-chemical properties of the pharmaceutical substance, its bioavailability, the type of dosage form, the route of administration, the nature of excipients, their compatibility, as well as the technological conditions of production, including when obtaining dosage forms. Before mass production of a medicinal product, the technological parameters and characteristics of the pharmaceutical substance must be thoroughly studied and scientifically justified. This paper is devoted to to study the technological properties of an original pharmaceutical substance based on dry extracts of rosehip, licorice root extract, raspberry leaf extract, currant leaf extract.

Keywords: fractional composition, flowability, bulk density, humidity, tablet, compressibility.

Relevance of the topic. Over the past two decades, interest in traditional systems of medicine, and especially in herbal medicines, has grown significantly in both developed and developing countries. The use of herbal preparations by the world's population is increasing every day in order to be closer to nature and avoid the negative impact of synthetic drugs. Medicinal raw materials and their preparations have not lost their relevance even now, during the victorious march of synthetic medicines. According to experts of the World Health Organization, about 1 million people die every year in the world due to complications associated with the use of medicines. It is no coincidence that the constant demand for herbal medicines around the world is explained by the demographic growth of senile people, the predominance of chronic diseases in the structure of morbidity, and increased awareness, which allows you to independently organize a strategy for your actions in the event of a disease. Based on the information mentioned earlier, we also decided to develop a plant-based drug technology. Another topical issue for today is the treatment of colds, speaking closer to our topic of inflammation of the upper respiratory tract. Most often, inflammation of the upper respiratory tract passes with coughing and sweating. After studying the information in the registers of Uzbekistan 2022 and 2023, it turned out that many expectorants of plant origin came out in the form of syrup, and very small amounts in the form of tablets, such as Mukaltin and licorice root tablets. Based on all the studies, we selected dry extracts of raspberry leaves, currant leaves, licorice root and rosehip fruits. Useful substances are generated in raspberry leaves, thanks to the process of photosynthesis, solar energy and nutritious soils.

Goal researches. The aim of the study was to study the technological characteristics of a pharmaceutical substance based on dry extracts of rosehip, licorice root extract, raspberry leaf extract, currant leaf extract.

Research methods: According to the ICH Q8 document, one of the stages of pharmaceutical development is aimed at studying the technological properties of individual active substances and excipients, in order to identify critical characteristics of starting materials that affect the quality of the finished product [1]. The results of this study are used to develop input control specifications, as well as to select and evaluate suppliers. The importance of such studies is determined by the fact that up to 50% of problems with the technology and quality of finished forms (granule flowability, tableting process, disintegration and solubility solid oral forms, etc.) depends on the components of the dosage form. It is well known that compliance with the pharmacopoeial requirements for active substances and excipients is not sufficient to ensure the stability of processes and the desired pharmacokinetic properties of many dosage forms. Since

the dosage during the tableting process is automatic, the powdery contents must first have good flowability, so that the powder can move by gravity from the hopper of the machine to the matrix of the tablet machine. Flowability, in turn, depends on many characteristics of the powder: from the fractional composition, amorphous nature and humidity of the substance. Since flowability is a complex characteristic, it is usually determined in two ways: by the flow rate from a standard funnel and by the value of the natural slope angle. Natural slope angle – the angle between the generatrix of a cone of bulk material and the horizontal plane. The slope angle characterizes the effect of friction between particles and the effect of gravity on the powder mass, gives an estimate of the effect of particle size, shape, and electrostatic interaction between particles during powder precipitation from the surface. bins of the capsule-filling machine [2]. The value of the natural slope angle depends on the shape, size, and cohesive properties of the particles; it varies widely: from 25° to 30° for well-bulk materials, and from 60° to 70° for poorly bulk materials [2,3]. Like other characteristics of bulk materials, the bulk density is a complex indicator that depends on many others: granulometric composition, humidity, density of laying in the layer. It is important that this is not a constant value, it can change under the influence of vibration and even when stored in a warehouse. Therefore, the minimum bulk density is distinguished free-filled powder and the maximum-bulk density after compaction - for powder that is freely filled, but has been compacted by shaking moisture, density of laying in a layer. It is important that this is not a constant value, it can change under the influence of vibration and even when stored in a warehouse. Therefore, a distinction is made between the minimum bulk density of a freely poured powder and the maximum-the bulk density after compaction - for powder that is freely poured, but has been compacted by shaking. Flowability and bulk density, being important characteristics of the powder mass in pharmaceutical technology, determine the rhythm and speed of the tablet machine, and, consequently, its productivity. In addition to the technological conditions, the flowability also affects the uniformity of the tablet mass.

Main results: Determination of the fractional composition was carried out in accordance with the GPhM.1.1.0015.15 "Screen analysis" at the ERWEKA PSS screen analysis facility, Germany. The exact weight of the material was divided into fractions by sieving through a set of sequentially assembled sieves with hole sizes: 2 mm, 1.25 mm, 710 microns and 315 microns. The suspension was placed on the top largest sieve and the entire set was shaken manually for 5 minutes. Then the sieves were removed one by one, and the material remaining on each screen was weighed separately. Then, the percentage of each fraction from the total weight of the sample was found. Sieving was considered complete if, with additional shaking, the amount of material passing through the screen for 1 minute was less than 1% by weight of the material remaining on the screen. The bulk density was determined in accordance with the GPhM.1.4.2.0016.15 "Powder flow rate" on the "SVM 121" bulk density tester from Erweka GmbH, Germany. During the analysis, a sample of the material was weighed with an accuracy of 0.001 g and filled into a glass measuring cylinder with a capacity of 25 ml. An oscillation amplitude of 3 mm and a frequency of 150 vibrations per minute were determined. After 5 minutes, the device was turned off. The bulk density was calculated by the formula: $\rho\rho = mm /v$, where p is the bulk density before or after shaking (compaction), g/cm³; m is the mass of the material, g; v is the volume of powder in the cylinder before or after shaking (compaction), cm³. Determination of flowability and natural slope angle was carried out in accordance with the GPhM.1.4.2.0016.15 "Powder flow rate" on the ERWEKA GTB flow tester, Germany. The exact weight of the powder, about 100 g., was poured into the funnel of the device, the nozzle diameter was 10 mm, and the sample expiration time was determined. The natural slope angle is set in the device using a laser sensor. The results obtained indicate low technological properties of the substance.

Conclusions. The characteristics of the substance can only be assessed as unsatisfactory. Based on the calculated values of the Carr and Hausner indices, the flowability of the substance is estimated as "very poor". Taking into account the low dosage of the substance, which necessitates the introduction of a significant amount of filler, sliding substance and disintegrant into the dosage

form, as well as due to low technological characteristics, it becomes necessary to granulate the powder mixture before tableting it to increase flowability and ensure uniformity.

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